

Trousers Model Architecture Church of Holy Family – Vadakkankulam

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Abstract

Catholic Church architectural patterns and features existed in a certain defined order. Every built environment has an implicit, and occasionally an explicit, theological meaning. It requires a certain type of lens in order to be able to see this, but there is no doubt that theological meaning is every where. For Catholics, this theological meaning is of ten easily seen in church architecture. The shape and design of a church emphasizes different aspects of theology. Examples include emphasizing the “body of Christ” or the “people of God” through spatial arrangements of seating, altar, and tabernacle. Church architecture used various elements that signified the true identity of Christian beliefs and culture. The church architecture uses various architectural features to communicate with God in proper manner of massiveness of the building structures or simple structural and architectural elements that are embraced with the contemporary churches. Vadakkankulam is the first parish of the inner most area that merged with Pearl Fishery Coast Mission and it was the last of the south western boarder of Madurai Mission. This article deals with the art and architecture of Holy Family Church which is located in Vadakkankulam.

Keywords: Architecture, Cruzadi, Trouserschurch, Traceries.

Introduction

Vadakkankulam is popularly called as “Little Rome” because of the profound activities and intense services of the Holy Family Church to the people of this locality. It is also famous for the two great towers of the church, by its heights which seem to touch the sky. The local tradition maintains that Vadakkankulam village which lies under the feet of the Western Ghats had its origin only in and around 1680 AD.¹ As the first immigrants to Vadakkankulam village is professed to be a Christian, so the origin of Christianity in Vadakkankulam owes to the same date. The Parish of Vadakkankulam is the first congregated Parish in the diocese of Thoothukudi. In addition to that this Church is more significant for it was one among the 14 early catholic churches congregated by the Madura Mission. Vadakkankulam is the first parish of the innermost area that merged with Pearl Fishery Coast Mission and it was the last of the south western boarder of Madurai Mission. This Church is historically significant since it was the first Nadar congregation of the Thoothukudi diocese and other importance of this Church is that it was one among the 14 churches congregated by the Jesuits in the Madurai province. In the last quarter of the 17th century, Vadakkankulam emerged to be a new village with the settlement of a Christian nodal lady in the foothills of the Western Ghats.

Origin of Christianity in Vadakkankulam

The origin of Christianity in Vadakkankulam and the origin of the village can be traced from a single event and it was a concurrent development. The village came into existence by the settlement of a lady named Sandhayi from the Eastern Coastal Area and as she belonged to the Christian religion Christianity got originated at Vadakkankulam after her arrival. About the year 1680 AD Sandhayi a Nadar caste woman along with her husband Gnanamuthu Nadar got settled at the forest area of Vadakkankulam.² Both of them were initiatively belonged to Catholic Christians. They had married their daughter to Ananda Nadar from Perungudi near Vadakkankulam village. Sandhayi did not like to live in the village, a place which was exclusively populated by the people belonged to Hindu religion. Therefore, she took refuge in the forest very close to Perungudi. At that time the place to which Sandhayi moved to settle was covered densely with trees and bushes, with an uneven land covered with irregular pits. The soil of the forest, in which Sandhayi settled, was very fertile. The first thing Sandhayi did in the middle of the forest was to construct a hut by cutting some of trees and plants. After making their abode to stay Sandhayi raised a Cruzadi with palm leaves facing her house. She lighted three candles always to be lighted in the Cruzadi. This Cruzadi had been dedicated to the Holy Family of Jesus Christ.

The year of 1684 AD can be considered as the first milestone in the history of Christianity in Vadakkankulam. It was in this year Sandhayi happened to meet Fr. John de Britto and it was he who congregated the Vadakkankulam Church. Sandhayi told the missionary about her settlement at this wild foresting a few words.³ She also requested him to visit her house and to bless the Cruzadi. Fr. De Britto was very excited to see a Christian family at the middle of the forest. She showed him her abode, the Cruzadi and the new village which was recently habituated with four other families. The father blessed the Cruzadi and their house with abstinent prayers. Subsequently Sandhayi solicited the missionary to construct a church within her settlement. De Britto also ensured to form a congregation here very soon. Sandhayi immediately started to construct a small Chapel about 12 feet

breadth and 20 feet length. The church was built with palm leaves at the place in which she firstly erected the Cruzadi. She gave the Holy Family as the patron of this Chapel. The first Church was built in 1695AD, second church appeared in 1752 AD and third one the present Church was built in 1872 AD.

Art and Architectural Features of the Church

The church which was constructed on 1872 is generally termed as Trousers Church because of its shape that looks like trousers.⁴ This Church had been built in this design so as to accommodate the two different caste groups separately but with one altar.

Partition Walls

The new church is of an eccentric design. Facing East, the church has its two inner naves in the shape of a V shape. The right nave is generally described as the southern Church and the left nave is Northern Church. These naves do not run parallel to one another from the altar but it is diverged from the altar at an angle of some 45 degree. This was a very unusual plan evidently from the result of the arrangements between two Caste groups. The worshippers in the two prayer naves are able to have a clear look upon the altar and the altar is facing the East. As usual there are aisles in an L shape parallel in front of the altar. Two walls about three and half feet height and 3/4 feet breadth were created in the Centre of the church. These walls started from the centre of the aisles and run towards the east forming a V shape. These dividing walls made the two halves of the church into two separate prayer places within the church. Both the dividing walls were considered as the double balustrade. There existed a way of passage for the Parish priest in between the balustrade.⁵ This way was used by the Parish priest to reach the altar by walking from the courtyard of the church. The design of the church resembles a pair of trousers each leg being reserved for a caste group. This is the reason for which this Holy Family Church at Vadakkankulam is called Trousers Church. The dividing walls were destructed by Fr. Coussanal in 1910 and after demolishing the walls now the church looks to be a great church. The church has a

well- built compound wall faces east. The main gate in the compound wall faces east along with those two more gates are there in the western side of the compound wall.

Right Nave of the Church

The altar faces the east as it was made so as to have a clear look from anywhere in the eastern doors of the church. The floorings of the altar were furnished with the best kind of mosaics. There is a great dome on the top of the altar and it has one minaret. Another glass tower also lies at the top centre of the altar. At present the altar is with 6 statues and they are as follows the statue of Jesus Christ as crucified in the cross is placed in the chief most place of the altar. The statues of Mother Mary and Joseph are also in the altar. Above these, the statues of St. Sebastian, St. Anthony and St. Francis Xavier have adorned the altar of the Holy Family Church. These statues were made from foreign countries and placed during the time of Fr. Swakin.

This Church has three main doors facing the eastern side. There are two side doors one each in the North and South. Another door is in the back side of the altar. Mostly the three doors facing the East are considered to be the main entrances of the church. All the wooden doors were embellished with great creative art works. There are 23 beautiful tracteries in the church. Initially these tracteries were fitted with unmatched plain glass. During the renovation for the centenary celebration all of them were replaced by well fitted and matching colourful glasses. These glasses give a very beautiful look to the church. There are totally 16 windows in all the sidewalls of the church. Originally these windows had benefitted very tightly as no air to enter into the church. All the sixteen remained closed under Jesuit father's administration. This was for the reasons of cold but now all the windows we refitted properly to get fresh air and sunlight to enter the church. Presently there are 24 arches in the interior of the church. As the church was builton Latin model, so each building received its own significance. The church earned great admiration by the structure of the arches. These arches were not built with cement and iron; instead, calcium carbonate and toddy were used to build these arches. No wooden pillar or beam

holds the arches. Undoubtedly these arches are of great specimens of the architecture. It was the plan of Brother Bergental, which still now gives a good adoration to the church. There is a joint of 12 arches at the top of the altar. There are two great high towers in the exterior of the church. Each tower is standing in the Northern and Southern sides of the main door. They are equal in size with the height of 92 feet. Both the towers had been designed with eight-fold edges in the outer side from the bottom to the top. At the steeple of the towers were fitted with two big mercury lights because they light on a vast portion in and around Vadakkankulam. Each tower holds a bronze bell hanged in the inner side of the towers. These bells were used during times of prayers and auspicious occasion. The steeples of the two towers seem to be very close to the sky. Vadakkankulam is said to have got its good name mainly because of the towers on the top of the church. There are sixteen small towers in all the borders of the church. They enhance the beauty of the church. By Latin influence these small towers were constructed. The interior of the church is adorned with marvelous paintings. They are more appealing than the other art of the church. In the inner top, arches and pillars were carved with wonderful paintings and all the paintings based on green meadows with flowers and natural scenery. One historical fact about these paintings is that they were not drawn with paints or chemicals but the artists used various natural dyes obtained from plants and trees. Because of that till today, the paintings of the church remain without defiling. So far it has not been repainted and it remains in its original form.

The church is also having music instruments like loud speakers and horns of facilitate the prayers with the songs. The church has marvelous lighting arrangements. Both inside and outside of the church is decorated with numerous lightings. The annual feast of the church is celebrated with Palanquin (chapparam) procession at the 10th day of the annual festival. A beautiful chapparam (Palanquin) is used to lead the procession. This Palanquin was made in 1890 with timbers of teak, vengai and kongu. This Palanquin has greatly engraved with art work and an altar is placed in its Centre. There is a flagstaff in front of the church. It is of 50 feet height. As a

mark of inaugurating the ten days feast usually flag is hoisted in the staff during its first day celebration. Mainly because of the structure and style of the Holy Family Church Vadakkankulam is popularly called as “Little Rome”. This church also serves as a centre of great spiritual activities from its establishment. The religious importance of the church also earned a great name to Vadakkankulam.

Conclusion

Holy Family Church is the most prominent pilgrimage centre in Vadakkankulam and one of the oldest churches in Tirunelveli district. The influence of the built environment upon humans has been noted throughout history. As Winston Churchill famously noted, “We shape our buildings, and afterwards our buildings shape us”.⁶ The origins of early Christianity and its growth are inherently urban. Our surrounding environment plays a role in the formation of our character, and the church plays a role in shaping that environment. Church architecture expresses theology. Instead of focusing

on interior design debates; it would behave us to think about the exterior of the church. This includes not only the style of architecture, but also the possibility of evangelization through art, as well as considering the surrounding environment and neighbourhood.

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